

MAIN WAYS TO ORGANIZE MILITARY-PATRIOTIC EDUCATION IN LIFELONG OPERATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In this article was informed about basic directions of organizing the pupil's military patriotism education in teaching establishment.

KEY WORDS

information, upbringing, education, military-patriotic upbringing, spiritual and moral, military-technical

Upgrading the theory and practice of military-patriotic education, training of military personnel, and defense of the homeland - the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the most important tasks of law enforcement training.

As long as serving our homeland, protecting our country, flourishing, flourishing and flourishing becomes our national consciousness, our ideals cannot be regained.

When we hear "Vatanparvar" and "Millatsevar", we will see the faces of our great ancestors Amir Temur, Shirok, Tumaris, Alpomysh, Jaloliddin Manguberder.

According to our president Sh.Mirziyoev, each generation builds on the history and reputation of the Jurassic, with the childhood love and belief, loyalty and creativity, courage and bravery.

Our main task is to educate the independent homeland of men and women, who are ready to live in peace, prosperity and freedom, for the sake of the people, and for the sake of self-sacrifice.

This education, of course, should be achieved through general education, namely, ethical, moral, labor, aesthetic, and physical activities.

The military-patriotic upbringing of Yugoslavia is an important part of the history. The military-patriotic education of the mother-people must be brought up in the spirit of loyalty and love to the people of Ona-Vatan, a well-known historical, peaceful and creative nation.

Life is engaged in security activities, military-patriotic and mass-defense measures will help lawmakers to provide the services of the Queen of the Tiger and the knowledge, skills, and skills needed to defend our homeland.

These activities and activities are based on the highest level of military education and service. They will learn the history of the Holy Quran, the activities that protect the independence of our homeland, the activities and duties of the Holy See, the service of the Holy See and much needed knowledge.

All social and political activities are singular and military-patriotic education also has a specific inventory and form.

Certain tasks, forms and styles of content, means, instruments, syndicate, specific functions can be fulfilled by the state and community, enterprises, organizations and institutions.

It is the task of educational institutions to form a complex character, that is, the patriotic spirit.

Second, he is irrevocable, as he has been influenced throughout his life.

For one thing, it is a complete form because it is based on the unity of the military and the army and the people.

The basic directions of military-patriotic education can be:

Moral and moral (psychological) readiness;

Military-technical training;

Practical and physical preparation.

In our opinion, the above mentioned three directions should form the modern system of military-patriotic education.

The following comments may be helpful:

1. If any state or army is physically, morally and spiritually composed, they will show their true love and devotion to the Motherland, if they are loyal to the Motherland. Such people or troops will never enter. After all, they are the ones who are spiritually gifted and who are spiritual. Such people are hard-working and hard-hitting, often failing, baffling, mischievous, and struggling for victory with all their means.

Historically, we know that the result of many battles was the spiritual state of the enduring war.

Therefore, our task is to educate the motherland in the spirit of self-reliance, the spiritual and spiritual training of the young generation, and for the sake of the country, its

independence and, if necessary, the self-sacrifice.

2. The army should be prepared not only for the moral and spiritual training, but also for the military-technical training. This personal composition is a skillful use of military knowledge and skills, disciplinary and disciplinary divisions, military oaths and military requirements, and the use of advanced military equipment and weapons.

Certainly, all of the above-mentioned military qualities are shaped by military-technical training, which is one of the main aspects of military-patriotic education.

In this work, educated in military-technical training of high-educated young people, the Vatanparvar organization should make a great contribution to their endeavors.

3. Military-patriotic education is one of the main directions of education of the youth. In this regard, the physical education, ie the military service, gives the impression that the letter can be used to record the physical convictions both during and after the military service.

Physicalism is not only a part of the Muslim world, but it is also a defense of the Motherland and a willingness to work. Contrary to current statistics, many do not meet their health and physical needs. The disadvantages are that many schools, lyceums and colleges, as well as high schools, and youth organizations are not well-educated.

At present, a number of laws and decrees in Uzbekistan have been adopted and enforced by the President and the government in order to overcome these problems and to freeze the physical education of the youth.

The formation of various religious extremist and intellectual groups for power, propagandizing world-wide ideas for the sake of business can pose a threat to the peace of our homeland, its peaceful and multinational people.

These groups should not support anyone who is indifferent to the corrupt propaganda of their youth.

As President Mirziyoev Sh.M. Moreover, in each of our business activities, it is

necessary to give a clear picture, in other words, a free system of military and patriotic education.

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